

The pH of $Cr(ClO_4)_3$ solution diminishes as the ageing proceeds (which is quite measurable if the pH of the solution was rather high). This is probably due to the reaction

The equilibration, however, achieves completion within a short time.

The works of King and co-workers⁵ show conclusively that when the pH of the solution is low, the hydrolytic equilibrium must be small enough to be neglected. To avoid the chance of our results being vitiated by the change in O.d. values, if any, due to aging, the measurements were taken at 260 and 270 nm where the change in O.d. values due to ageing (under our experimental conditions) has been found to be very small (within experimental errors).

The amount of complex formed at various intervals of time can be determined in the same way as described before⁴. However, for the kinetic measurement in this case, we are concerned with the change $d_t - d_0$ with time. O.d. values were found to vary linearly with time. The o.d. values at different time intervals were plotted against time for each set of solution (Fig. 1) and extrapolated to zero time to have d_0 values. However, there is slight discrepancy in the O.d. values obtained at the time of mixing and the extra-polated value at zero time. The values of d_t at various time intervals at 270 nm and $\frac{d_t - d_0}{t}$ values for a number of solutions are given in Table 1. For any solution at a particular pH , it has been found that $\frac{d_t - d_0}{t}$ is a constant quantity within experimental errors. The rate of reaction

Fig. 1. Wavelength = 270 nm
Ionic strength = 0.25M

	[Cr(ClO ₄) ₃]	[H ₃ PO ₄]	pH
I.	0.006M	0.006M	1.97
II.	0.012M	0.010M	1.80
III.	0.015M	0.015M	1.73
IV.	0.020M	0.024M	1.56

has been found to be independent of the concentrations of the substance taking part in the reaction. Thus, the reaction between chromic ion and phosphoric acid is a zero-order reaction under our experimental conditions. It has been found that the equilibrium is reached in about 700 hr but the reaction in the region 500–700 hr is not a zero-order reaction. More detailed study are necessary to have a definite say regarding the order of the reaction in this region.

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Chemisorption of Nitrogen by Carbon Blacks on Treatment with Dimethylamine

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THE influence of combined oxygen in enhancing adsorption of ammonia, methylamine and other amines by carbons has been attributed either to formation of hydrogen-bonds¹ of these compounds with the constituents of oxygen complex or to their neutralization at the acidic sites on the surface provided by CO₂-complex. The possibility of chemisorption of nitrogen² in the process has not been explored. The present work describes fixation of nitrogen on treatment of sugar and coconut shell charcoals outgassed at different temperatures with dimethylamine in aqueous solution as well as gaseous state. For the reaction in solution phase, it was found convenient to mix 1 g. charcoal with 100 ml of 0.305N solution and to shake the suspension mechanically for a period of 72 hr. For the reaction in gaseous phase, dimethylamine obtained by warming aqueous solution (40%) and dried over fused

TABLE I—CHEMISORPTION OF NITROGEN BY CHARCOALS IN RELATION TO THEIR OXYGEN CONTENTS

Description of the sample	Oxygen contents evolved on outgassing as		Nitrogen fixed on treatment with dimethylamine in		Ratio of N ₂ fixed to O ₂ as CO-complex	
	CO ₂ mg.atom/g	CO mg.atom/g	Solution phase mg.atom/g	Gaseous phase mg.atom/g	Reaction in solution phase	Reaction ⁱⁿ gaseous phase
Sugar charcoal, original	105.6	86.9	25.7	27.6	0.296	0.318
-do- outgassed at 300°	61.1	77.1	22.8	26.1	0.295	0.338
-do- outgassed at 400°	29.7	70.2	20.7	21.2	0.295	0.302
-do- outgassed at 500°	22.4	56.7	10.8	16.9	0.191	0.300
-do- outgassed at 700°	nil	29.4	9.3	10.2	0.317	0.318
-do- outgassed at 1000°	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil
Coconut shell charcoal, original	71.6	77.2	21.7	14.4	0.281	0.188
-do- outgassed at 400°	12.7	59.2	11.718	13.6	0.196	0.230
-do- outgassed at 700°	nil	28.4	1.792	9.1	0.060	0.318
-do- outgassed at 1000°	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil

calcium oxide was led @ 1 l./hr. over charcoal bed (5 g) held in a rotating pyrex glass tube of 3/4" bore heated to 200° in a resistance tube furnace for a period of 8 hours. The results are recorded in Table I, It is seen that the amount of nitrogen fixed by a charcoal on reacting it with dimethylamine in gaseous phase or solution phase decreases with fall in its oxygen content on outgassing at increasing temperatures. The value falls to zero as the oxygen is eliminated completely at 1000°. The amount of nitrogen fixed does not appear to be related to oxygen evolved as CO₂ (i.e., CO₂-complex). However, the nitrogen fixed seems to be related to oxygen present as CO-complex as the ratio between the two in most cases

in almost the same. Since this complex is believed to be constituted by quinonic and phenolic groups, it appears that fixation of nitrogen by carbons on treatment with dimethylamine arises through interaction at the sites provided by phenolic and quinonic groups.

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